

Correlation between Diagnostic Nasal Endoscopy and CT Features of Chronic Rhinosinusitis**Harun Khan¹, Man Prakash Sharma², Falguni Tyagi³, Seyad Mohammad Ibrahim⁴, Porshia Rishi⁵**¹3rd Year PG Resident, Dept. of ENT, National Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Jaipur²Professor, Dept. of ENT, National Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Jaipur³3rd Year PG Resident, Dept. of ENT, National Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Jaipur⁴3rd Year PG Resident, Dept. of ENT, National Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Jaipur⁵Senior Resident, Dept. of ENT, National Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Jaipur

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 23-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Introduction:** Chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS) is a persistent inflammatory disease of the nasal and paranasal sinuses affecting 5% to 12% of the population, leading to significant morbidity. Accurate diagnosis using nasal endoscopy and CT scans is crucial for effective management. This study explores the correlation between these diagnostic tools to optimize CRS treatment, particularly in resource-limited settings.**Aim and objectives:** This study aims to correlate between the diagnostic nasal endoscopic features (Lund-Kennedy) and CT features (Lund-Mackay) in patients with chronic rhinosinusitis.**Method:** This 18-month prospective study at the National Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Jaipur, involved 162 participants to investigate Chronic Rhinosinusitis (CRS). A comprehensive approach was used, incorporating clinical history, Diagnostic Nasal Endoscopy (DNE) with the Lund-Kennedy score (≥ 2), and CT scans with the Lund-Mackay score (≥ 4) for diagnosis. Inclusion criteria included patients over 14, excluding those with facial abnormalities and pregnant women.**Results:** The study involved 162 participants, predominantly in the 15-34 age group. Gender distribution was nearly equal, with 83 males and 79 females. The study has shown that the most patients had mild to moderate sinus involvement, with 48.8% scoring 2 on the Lund-Kennedy Endoscopic Scoring System and 41.4% scoring 3, while a small subset exhibited severe pathology. Significant correlations were found between facial pain/pressure and sinusitis severity ($p=0.000$), and nasal discharge/purulence ($p=0.004$). Elevated heart rate and blood pressure were also noted.**Conclusion:** The study concluded that there is statistically significant correlation between the diagnostic nasal endoscopic features (Lund-Kennedy) and CT features (Lund-Mackay) in patients with chronic rhinosinusitis**Keywords:** Chronic Rhinosinusitis, Nasal Endoscopy, CT Correlation, Lund-Kennedy Score, Sinusitis Diagnosis.

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Introduction

Chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS) is an inflammatory disease of mucosa in the nasal and paranasal sinuses (PNS) that stays for 12 weeks or more [1]. The prevalence differs greatly across regions but ranges between 5% and 12% of the population [2], considerably reducing the quality of life among patients with CRS [3,4]. It is a major cause of morbidity, causing social awkwardness, decreased productivity at school or work, and an economic burden from lost workdays and medical visits. Accurate diagnosis and timely management are therefore very important in decreasing morbidity related to CRS [5]. CRS occurs in many forms, with inflammatory thickening of the sinonasal mucosa at one end and extensive formation of polyps at the other end of

the spectrum. Based on the findings in endoscopy, the European Position Paper on Rhinosinusitis and Nasal Polyps 2012 defined CRS as two broad categories: CRS with nasal polyps and CRS without nasal polyps [6]. New guidelines regarding the diagnosis and management of CRS were published by the American Academy of Otolaryngology-Head and Neck Surgery in 2007 that suggest the patients with two or more of these symptoms—mucopurulent drainage, nasal obstruction, facial pain or pressure, or a decreased sense of smell, for whom CT scan of the nose and PNS with diagnostic nasal endoscopy is recommended. These investigative tools are essential in assessing the severity of the disease and guiding treatment planning [7].

A diagnosis of CRS is based on clinical features associated with evidence of inflammation noted on nasal endoscopy and/or CT of the paranasal sinuses [1]. CT scans are also helpful for careful evaluation of localized disease or anatomic abnormalities that may affect ventilation and mucociliary clearance, and therefore help the surgeon decide the when and where of the operation. While CT scans give detailed information on the extent of the disease and anatomical variants, nasal endoscopy is an affordable routine investigation that helps assess the progression of the sinus disease. Many studies have shown that there is a close correlation between the findings of DNE and CT scan nasal and PNS. These together have considerably improved the understanding and treatment of CRS [8]. Nasal endoscopy gives an excellent, illuminated view of the nasal cavity and nasopharynx to enable proper examination, while the CT scans give an excellent and complete imaging of both intranasal and intraluminal sinus anatomy [9,10]. Several studies have documented varying degrees of concordance of the nasal endoscopy findings with the CT scan result in patients with CRS, mainly in developed countries where these diagnostic tools have been in service for quite a considerable number of years [11–14].

Since the nature of healthcare payments in developing regions is out-of-pocket, there is a need to estimate the sensitivity, specificity and prognostic values of nasal endoscopy compared to CT scans. Of interest to all clinicians is how diagnostic nasal endoscopy findings correlate with CT features of CRS. Such knowledge allows optimization of diagnostic accuracy and avoidance of radiation exposure from a CT if this is not otherwise indicated, and generally it will dictate treatment strategies. This introduction gives way to explore how these two diagnostic modalities complement, their strengths and limitations, and what it all means for clinical practice in the management of chronic rhinosinusitis.

The present study focuses on assessing and then correlating the nasal endoscopy and CT-scan findings in adult patients suffering from CRS, thereby guiding more toward an effective diagnostic approach, especially in resource-constrained settings.

Method

Research Design: This prospective study involved 162 participants admitted to the National Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Jaipur, over approximately 18 months, from July 1, 2022, to December 31, 2023. The study aimed to investigate Chronic Rhinosinusitis (CRS) in patients who met specific criteria. A comprehensive approach was employed, involving the collection of clinical history and detailed analysis. Symptom severity was measured using a visual analog scale, with scores

ranging from 0 to 10. Patients underwent Diagnostic Nasal Endoscopy and CT scans of the nose and paranasal sinuses (PNS), with outcomes carefully documented.

Chronic rhinosinusitis was diagnosed based on the Lund-Kennedy endoscopic score, with scores of ≥ 2 considered significant. The Lund-Mackay CT scoring system was also used, with a score of ≥ 4 serving as the diagnostic threshold. This dual diagnostic approach provided a thorough evaluation, integrating both endoscopic and radiological findings. Inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied to ensure a homogeneous study population.

The clinical records and analysis data provided a complex baseline, offering a detailed understanding of each patient's condition. The visual analog scale for symptom scoring facilitated a quantitative assessment of symptom severity, enabling standardized evaluation across the patient cohort. The use of Diagnostic Nasal Endoscopy and CT scans added objectivity to the diagnostic process, enhancing the reliability of the results. This study design, which integrates clinical, endoscopic, and radiological parameters, aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of CRS and contribute valuable insights to the medical community.

Inclusion and Exclusion

Inclusion

- All chronic rhinosinusitis patients above 14.
- Participants or guardians who consent to the study.

Exclusion

- Individuals presenting with facial abnormalities.
- Pregnant female patients

Statistical Analysis: SPSS and Excel will be used for data analysis. The statistical analysis will examine the data thoroughly to gain insights. Statistics will be used in SPSS and Excel to find patterns, correlations, and trends in the dataset. Statistical approaches will be applied to the data to ensure the best analyses. This analysis seeks to provide a solid and trustworthy interpretation of the acquired data using SPSS and Excel, helping to grasp the underlying patterns and phenomena.

Result

Figure 1 shows the age distribution of 162 research participants. There are 54 patients in the 15–24 age group and 53 in the 25–34 age group, making up the bulk of the patient population. There are 48 patients in the 35–44 age group, and the smallest group, consisting of only 7 people, is those older than 45. The demographic mix is clearly shown by this age-wise breakdown, which shows that the

majority of participants are in the younger age categories. This might be a reflection of the beginning

or prevalence of Chronic Rhinosinusitis in this particular study population.

Figure 1: The number of patients in each age range

Figure 2 shows the gender distribution of the 162 research participants. Patient numbers are 83 male and 79 female. A balanced gender representation in the research cohort promotes a full knowledge of Chronic Rhinosinusitis (CRS) in both male and

female populations. Gender parity ensures that gender-specific variables do not distort observations and conclusions, making the research reliable and applicable across broad demographic groups suffering CRS.

Figure 2: Gender distribution of the patients in this study

Figure 3 shows the main complaints that the 162 people who took part in this research had. The most common complaint is headache, which 36 people have reported. Next on the list are nasal obstruction and auditory problems, which 29 people have experienced. Some 28 people are worried about throat irritation, while 24 people are worried about facial

pain. For sixteen people, the most common symptoms are bleeding and nasal discharge. The many symptoms that Chronic Rhinosinusitis (CRS) patients experience are highlighted by this breakdown, which highlights the need for a comprehensive evaluation and individualised treatment plans.

Figure 3: Chief Complaints of the patients in this study

Figure 4 shows the participants' medical histories for the 162 individuals that were studied. The most common chronic ailment reported by patients is hypertension (33 cases), followed closely by tuberculosis (28 cases). There are 27 cases of rhinitis and 26 cases of diabetes. Asthma affects 23 people

and Group A Staphylococcus affects 25 patients. This analysis highlights the fact that Chronic Rhinosinusitis often occurs with other chronic illnesses, highlighting the need to take comorbidities into account when trying to fully understand and treat this nose and sinus ailment.

Figure 4: Number of patients with history of chronic diseases

Table 1 presents the average Visual Analog Scale (VAS) scores for various clinical features, both major and minor symptoms, experienced by the patients in this study. The most prominent symptom is nasal obstruction or blockage, with an average VAS score of 6.19 ± 2.65 , indicating a moderate to severe level of discomfort. Nasal discharge or purulence and discolored postnasal drainage also scored relatively high at 4.4 ± 2.03 , reflecting significant patient concern. Other symptoms with notable

average scores include hyposmia or anosmia (4.04 ± 1.52), halitosis (4.38 ± 2.84), and headache (3.34 ± 3.06). On the lower end, ear pain/pressure/fullness had the lowest average score at 1.05 ± 0.9 , suggesting that this symptom was less prevalent or less severe among the patient group. Facial pain/pressure, facial congestion/fullness, fatigue, cough, and dental pain were also reported but with lower average VAS scores, indicating varying levels of impact on the patients' quality of life.

Table 1: Average Scores of the Clinical Features as found in patients of this study

Clinical Features (Major and Minor Symptoms)	Average VAS
Facial pain/pressure	2.4±3.1
Facial congestion/fullness	2.27±2.11
Nasal obstruction/blockage	6.19±2.65
Nasal discharge/purulence, discolored post nasal drainage	4.4±2.03
Hyposmia/anosmia	4.04±1.52
Headache	3.34±3.06
Halitosis	4.38±2.84
Fatigue	2.93±1.85
Cough	3.22±1.73
Ear pain/pressure/fullness	1.05±0.9
Dental pain	3.12±1.7

Table 2 provides the mean values of several vital parameters measured among the patients. The average systolic blood pressure is recorded at 134.47±6.93 mmHg, while the diastolic pressure averages 94.63±2.76 mmHg, both of which are slightly elevated from normal ranges. The mean heart rate is notably high at 130.23±5.5 beats per minute, which could indicate underlying stress or

health issues. The average respiratory rate is 21±1.98 breaths per minute, which is within the normal range. The average body temperature is 37.43±0.33°C, suggesting that most patients were afebrile. The patients' average weight and height are 70.86±9.01 kg and 170.3±6.01 cm, respectively, providing a general profile of the study population's physical characteristics.

Table 2: Mean value of the parameters of the patients

Parameters	Mean Value
Blood Pressure (Systole)	134.47±6.93
Blood Pressure (Diastole)	94.63±2.76
Heart Rate	130.23±5.5
Respiratory Rate	21±1.98
Temperature	37.43±0.33
Weight	70.86±9.01
Height	170.3±6.01

Figure 5 shows the distribution of patients according to the Lund-Mackay score (above) and Lund-Kennedy Endoscopic Scoring System (below). The above figure represents the results of the CT scan. With 138 cases in total, the majority had a score of 2, suggesting that the level of participation is frequent. Scores of 1 indicate less severe sinus involvement in 19 cases. A smaller subset of 5 individuals, however, receives a score of 3, indicating that their Chronic Rhinosinusitis is more prominently visible on radiographs. The distribution of moderate involvement is highlighted by this breakdown, which helps to classify and comprehend the level of sinus disease in the research group. In the analyzed cohort of 162 patients assessed using the Lund-Kennedy Endoscopic Scoring System, the

distribution of scores illustrates varying degrees of nasal polyposis and mucosal inflammation. Minimal pathology, reflected by a score of 1, was observed in 11 patients (6.8%). The majority, comprising 79 individuals (48.8%), exhibited mild disease with a score of 2. Moderate pathology, characterized by a score of 3, was present in 67 patients (41.4%). However, only a small proportion showed more severe manifestations, with 2 individuals (1.2%) scoring a 4 and 3 patients (1.9%) obtaining a score of 5, indicating extensive disease burden. Overall, the distribution suggests that most patients in the study have mild to moderate nasal polyposis and mucosal inflammation, with a minority presenting with severe pathology.

Figure 5: (above) Number of patients with respect to Lund-Mackay score; (below) Number of patients with respect to Lund-Kennedy score

Table 3 presents the significance findings between key clinical parameters and the Lund-Mackay and Lund-Kennedy scoring systems, which are used to assess sinusitis severity. Facial pain/pressure shows a highly significant correlation with both scoring systems, with p-values of 0.000, indicating a strong association with sinusitis severity. Nasal discharge/purulence also demonstrates a significant

correlation with p-values of 0.004 and 0.003 for the Lund-Mackay and Lund-Kennedy scores, respectively. In contrast, facial congestion/fullness and nasal obstruction/blockage exhibit weaker correlations, with p-values above the typical significance threshold of 0.05, suggesting that these symptoms are less strongly associated with the severity of sinusitis as measured by these scoring systems.

Table 3: Significance findings between the parameters

Parameters	Lund Mackay	Lund Kennedy
Facial pain pressure	0.000	0.000
Facial congestion fullness	0.332	0.338
Nasal obstruction blockage	0.054	0.065
Nasal discharge purulence	0.004	0.003

Discussion

CRS is a very common entity, and worldwide, its prevalence continues to rise. Although the diagnosis of CRS is based mainly on clinical manifestations, the team from the American Academy of Otolaryngology advocated that nasal endoscopy and CT scan of nose and para nasal sinuses be done for a better diagnosis and management of this disease [7].

CRS is also more commonly seen in females, which could be because of the difference in size,

susceptibility to tobacco, hormonal influences, other factors, or a combination of all these possibilities that increase the susceptibility in women. In addition, women could be more prone to obstruction or an infection through small sinus ostia [15,16]. The most common symptoms found in the study are nasal obstruction and nasal discharge, which is quite compatible with the studies conducted by Nayak et al. [17] and Deosthale et al. [18], which also found these two symptoms as the most common among CRS cases.

The commonest symptoms observed were rhinorrhea and nasal obstruction, which were consistent with other CRS studies [4,19]. Nasal endoscopy frequently showed cream-colored discharge and mucosal edema in the middle meatus with purulent discharge, based on some studies (20–22). Some other studies found nasal polyps to be the most common [23].

Baruah (24) and Neto [25] et al. showed CT scans obstruction in the osteomeatal complex (OMC) in 61.2% and 65% of the patients, respectively. The proclivity is mostly in the maxillary sinus, followed by the ethmoidal sinus, and the least involved is the sphenoid sinus [23,26,27]. Pansinusitis can be associated with sinus opacification rather than mucosal thickening, indicating more severe disease [23,27]. Polyps were detected in 32.5 percent by nasal endoscopy and in 14.2 percent by a CT scan, as the endoscope often shows a far better view of those small polyps [28,29].

In the study by Uwaneme, nasal endoscopy was 73.3% sensitive and 85.3% specific, with a positive prognostic value of 92.7% and a negative prognostic value of 55.8% [22]. This implies that, although nasal endoscopy is a good diagnostic tool for CRS, its negative result does not totally exclude the condition and, for this reason, a CT scan may as well be justified. Thus, symptoms-based diagnosis with the addition of endoscopy significantly increased the accuracy, although some authors advocate the CT necessity particularly with endoscopy findings negative [30]. CT scans are highly sensitive in the detection of changes in the nasal and PNS mucosa, but may sometimes overestimate the severity of the disease, especially in the presence of polypoidal mucosa [31]. Clifton et al. cautioned against operating asymptomatic patients based on CT findings, as the abnormalities can be detected in up to 30% of asymptomatic individuals [32]. Hence, correlation of the symptom with the CT finding is a prerequisite to proceed with any surgical management.

Deosthale et al., found a correlation coefficient of 0.881 ($p < 0.0001$) between Lund-Mackay CT score and Lund-Kennedy endoscopy score [33]. In fact, Rosbe et al. also observed that positive endoscopic result were significantly associated with positive CT scan findings [34]. Similarly, high agreement of endoscopy with CT scan, kappa greater than 0.800 and 0.700, respectively, were shown to have an accord or strong correlation of the findings in endoscopy with CT in CRS, in studies by Buljeik-Cupic and Savović, respectively [35].

Although CT of the nasal and PNS is said to be the gold diagnostic test for CRS, it is not routinely recommended because of its cost and exposure to radiation. It would be better to reserve the CT for patients with positive symptoms or those who, on

follow-up, have negative findings on endoscopy but became symptomatic. CT is especially helpful in cases wherein there are severe anatomical abnormalities that make endoscopic navigation difficult [36].

Diagnostic nasal endoscopy is an early effective diagnostic tool in the assessment of CRS in the setting of frank purulent discharge or polyps within the middle meatus. However, in a case of negative endoscopy, a confirmation may require CT scanning. CT scans are reserved for patients in whom positive symptoms are demonstrated, either as a secondary investigation for those with a negative endoscopic result who later go on to develop symptoms.

Conclusion

The study concluded that there is statistically significant correlation between the diagnostic nasal endoscopic features (Lund-Kennedy) and CT features (Lund-Mackay) in patients with chronic rhinosinusitis. The study has shown that the facial pain/pressure and nasal discharge/purulence are strongly correlated with CRS severity, as measured by both the Lund-Mackay and Lund-Kennedy scoring systems. These findings reinforce the importance of these symptoms in assessing and managing CRS. Overall, this study's findings contribute to a deeper understanding of CRS, supporting the need for comprehensive and tailored therapeutic strategies that address the complex interplay of symptoms and comorbidities in affected patients. The Lund-Mackay scores suggest frequent but generally mild to moderate radiographic involvement, with a smaller subset of patients showing more severe disease. Similarly, the Lund-Kennedy scores highlight that most patients have mild to moderate nasal polyposis and mucosal inflammation, with few cases of severe pathology. The analysis of clinical parameters reveals a strong correlation between facial pain/pressure and nasal discharge/purulence with the severity of sinusitis, as measured by both scoring systems, while facial congestion/fullness and nasal obstruction/blockage show weaker associations. Overall, these results underscore the importance of facial pain and nasal discharge as key indicators of sinusitis severity in clinical assessments.

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